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Predicting Bike Rental Demand for Smarter Urban Mobility

SEOBIKE

Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Deliverable abstract

Predicting Bike Rental Demand for Smarter Urban Mobility has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. .

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Predicting Bike Rental Demand for Smarter Urban Mobility project, delivered in [M4]. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the [section name] section.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

[name of data manager] will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	seoul_bike_with_splits.csv	Plain text	text/plain	100 - 1000 MB	no

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Seoul Bike Sharing Demand	10.24432/C5F62R	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)	no

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The research data used in this project comes from the publicly available Seoul Bike Sharing Demand dataset, which includes historical bike rental counts along with environmental and temporal features, such as temperature, humidity, wind speed, and the time of day.

Data Generation:

Original Dataset:

10.24432/C5F62R (<https://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/560/seoul+bike+sharing+demand>) The usage is allowed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International.

The original data was extended by adding additional information for regression and forecasting splits. This makes reproducible research possible, because the usually randomised data split is known by everyone.

Throughout the experiment subset of the data are produced by executing SQL queries in DBRepo. These queries mainly filter the dataset according to a column that is already specified in the raw data uploaded to DBRepo.

Besides that for future usage of the generated model weather forecasts and static information like seasons can be generated for a time of interest.

The following dataset is used for training the model:

[10.82556/mk3x-qa86 DBRepo](#)

The data is divided into the following subsets:

Training subset: [10.82556/kwdw-0f97](#)

Validation subset: [10.82556/3v3n-tc66](#)

Test subset: [10.82556/v8zn-p156](#)

Link to DBrepo (Test instance): <https://test.dbrepo.tuwien.ac.at/database/674930b1-c199-4f3a-aa57-7ba55445bcd2/info>

Data Preprocessing:

Missing Data Handling: There is no missing data.

Feature Engineering: New features are derived, including a "date and hour" column representing the timestamp for bike rentals. Categorical variables like season, holiday status, and functioning day are one-hot encoded to make them usable for machine learning models.

Data Splitting: The dataset is split into training, validation, and test sets. The data is split temporally (preserving the time sequence) to avoid data leakage. This ensures the model is tested on data that it has not been exposed to during training.

Data Reuse:

The primary dataset used in the project is the Seoul Bike Sharing Demand dataset, which is reused for training machine learning models, evaluating their performance, and making predictions on future bike rental demand.

Methods:

Data Preprocessing and Feature Engineering:

Data cleaning steps include dropping unnecessary columns and handling missing values.

Feature encoding transforms categorical columns into one-hot encoded features, while numeric columns are prepared for model training.

Model Training:

XGBoost: The primary algorithm used for training is XGBoost, a gradient boosting algorithm suitable for regression tasks like predicting bike rental demand. Model parameters such as learning rate (eta), tree depth (max_depth), and early stopping criteria are optimized during training.

Cross-validation: The model is trained on the training set and validated using a validation set. Early stopping is applied to prevent overfitting.

Model Evaluation:

The trained model's performance is evaluated using metrics like Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE). These metrics assess the accuracy of the predictions compared to the actual bike rental counts.

Software and Tools:

The following software and libraries will be used to carry out the data preprocessing, modeling, and evaluation:

Python programming language with the following libraries:

Pandas for data manipulation and preprocessing

NumPy for numerical operations

XGBoost for training the regression model

Matplotlib for creating visualizations of model performance

Scikit-learn for any additional preprocessing and model evaluation

Jupyter Notebooks for interactive development and documentation of the analysis.

This combination of methods and tools will ensure the successful generation, processing, and analysis of data, allowing for the development of accurate predictive models for bike rental demand.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Decision makers in industry

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Data will be findable by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

The respective work package leader will handle the structure and versioning of the research data.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used [at file level/at dataset level/at project level]. This will help others to identify, discover, and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data. In this case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests. Some datasets cannot be published and even need to be deleted at the end of the project. See section 5 for more details.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2025-04-30	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset

published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: Users may need tools such as Python (pandas, xgboost, scikit-learn), R, or SQL clients (e.g., MySQL Workbench, DBeaver) for data analysis. For visualization, Matplotlib, Seaborn, or Tableau may be required. If using versioned data from DBRepo, users will need access to its web interface or compatible APIs.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions will include details on the methodology used, analytical, and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained will be published Open

Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided that there are no data protection concerns.

Clear Dataset Metadata: Each table and its subsets will include detailed metadata, describing the data's origin, purpose, and transformations. This metadata will follow established standards (e.g., FAIR principles) and include:

Dataset versioning (e.g., "Seoul Bike demand data", "Seoul Bike demand data v1")

Data collection methods and sources

Description of each column and its meaning (e.g., `rented_bike_count`, temperature, season)

Data cleaning and preprocessing steps

Use of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs): Datasets will be assigned Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) to ensure traceability and reproducibility. This will make it easier to reference the datasets in publications and ensure they can be accessed over time.

Comprehensive Documentation in Repositories:

Code, data, and metadata will be stored in a public repository (e.g., GitHub or DBRepo) with clear README files, documenting the data processing pipeline, model-building steps, and any assumptions made.

Version history and changelogs will be maintained to track any modifications to the datasets or models.

Data Provenance Tracking: A record of data transformations (e.g., filtering, encoding, feature extraction) will be maintained to ensure reproducibility. This will be documented in both the dataset's metadata and in code comments.

Interactive Dashboards or Visualizations: To further facilitate data analysis and reuse, interactive visualizations and dashboards will be made available, summarizing key insights from the data. These visualizations will provide context on how the data was processed and what it represents.

Standardized Formats and File Structure: Data will be stored in widely accepted formats (e.g., CSV, JSON, Parquet) with clear folder structures to organize raw data, processed data, and analysis results, ensuring accessibility and usability.

Licensing Information: Proper licensing (e.g., MIT, CC BY) will be included to clarify how the data and results can be reused, providing clear terms for reuse while respecting intellectual property rights.

The following data quality checks will be done: standardised data capture.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

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4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Coverage of costs:

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The data manager will direct the data management process overall, with [the work package leaders] being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, backup and other quality control activities are maintained. The researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Lukas Kobler (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU Wien's Campus IT. The data will be stored on TU Wien servers.

R1 (Seoul Bike Sharing Demand) will be stored on TUfiles: TUfiles is a central and readily

available network drive with daily backups and regular snapshots provided by TU.it. It is suitable for storing data with moderate access requirements, but high availability demands that allows full control of allocating authorisations. Only authorized staff members will have access.

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	no access
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1. Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and rights of use

The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data: Regarding the created version in dbrepo there is only one contributor who can control the access.

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?